

LETTER • **OPEN ACCESS**

Increasing spatial extent and frequency of flash drought in Europe with each degree of global warming

To cite this article: Devvrat Yadav *et al* 2025 *Environ. Res. Lett.* **20** 114046

View the [article online](#) for updates and enhancements.

You may also like

- [Regional characteristics of flash droughts across the United States](#)
Jordan I Christian, Jeffrey B Basara, Jason A Otkin *et al.*
- [Increasing risk of simultaneous occurrence of flash drought in major global croplands](#)
Shanti Shwarup Mahto and Vimal Mishra
- [Beyond one-size-fits-all: a path toward region-specific flash drought monitoring and management](#)
Gabriela Gesualdo and Antonia Hadjmichael

The Electrochemical Society
Advancing solid state & electrochemical science & technology

**249th
ECS Meeting**
May 24-28, 2026
Seattle, WA, US
*Washington State
Convention Center*

Spotlight Your Science

**Submission deadline:
December 5, 2025**

SUBMIT YOUR ABSTRACT

ENVIRONMENTAL RESEARCH
LETTERS

LETTER

Increasing spatial extent and frequency of flash drought in Europe with each degree of global warming

Devvrat Yadav^{1,*}
and Oldrich Rakovec^{1,*} ¹ Faculty of Environmental Sciences, Czech University of Life Sciences Prague, Kamýcká 1176, 165 00 Praha-Suchdol, Czech Republic² Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research GmbH—UFZ, Department Computational Hydrosystems, Permoserstraße 15, 04318 Leipzig, Germany³ Department of Physical Geography, Utrecht University, PO Box 80.115, 3508 TC Utrecht, The Netherlands⁴ T.G. Masaryk Water Research Institute, Podbabska 30, Praha 6 16000, Czech Republic

* Authors to whom any correspondence should be addressed.

E-mail: yadavd@fzp.czu.cz and rakovec@fzp.czu.cz**Keywords:** flash droughts, global warming levels, soil moisture, Paris agreement, IPCC, EuropeSupplementary material for this article is available [online](#)RECEIVED
23 June 2025REVISED
22 September 2025ACCEPTED FOR PUBLICATION
10 October 2025PUBLISHED
24 October 2025Original Content from
this work may be used
under the terms of the
[Creative Commons
Attribution 4.0 licence](#).Any further distribution
of this work must
maintain attribution to
the author(s) and the title
of the work, journal
citation and DOI.**Abstract**

Flash droughts, characterised by sudden and severe development of dry soil moisture conditions, have detrimental impacts on agriculture and ecosystems. Since reliable projections of any kind of drought are crucial for drought risk mitigation, studying how these flash droughts evolve as warming increases becomes essential. Herein, we analyse changes in flash drought frequency, geographic extent, and regional variability across Europe under incremental global warming levels of 1 °C, 1.5 °C, 2 °C and 3 °C. Soil moisture simulations are obtained using the mesoscale hydrologic model (mHM), which has been forced with the bias-corrected meteorological data from ISIMIP3b (Inter-Sectoral Impact Model Intercomparison Project, phase 3b). We use a percentile-based method to determine the rapid decline in soil moisture conditions during the growing season. Our results show that Northern and Central Europe are expected to see more frequent flash drought events at higher warming levels above 1.5 °C. As temperatures increase, new areas experience flash drought in Central Europe. In contrast, the increase in frequency and area is less in the Mediterranean. Across Europe, we expect the mean frequency of flash droughts to increase from around 3 events each decade at 1 °C to 5 events at 3 °C. The median value of the spatial area covered in flash drought is expected to increase from around 30% at 1 °C to close to 44% at 3 °C. Each degree of increase in warming is expected to add around one more flash drought event each decade and more than 6% of the area across Europe under flash drought. The threshold of 1.5 °C marks a significant increase in the area affected by flash droughts, highlighting the importance of adhering to the Paris Agreement targets and adaptation measures to counter such flash drought conditions and safeguard the agricultural economy, food security, and ecosystems.

1. Introduction

Droughts are one of the most complex and least understood natural hazards (Pulwarty and Sivakumar 2014). Among them, ‘flash’ droughts have emerged as distinct and concerning climatic extremes. Flash droughts can be characterised by rapid onset and intensification in a span of a few weeks, unlike conventional soil moisture droughts in which there could be a gradual increase in soil moisture deficit for months or years, posing a challenge to monitoring

and forecasting capabilities (e.g. Otkin *et al* 2018, Christian *et al* 2019, Yuan *et al* 2019). Insufficient early warning exposes a different set of vulnerabilities in our agricultural system (Goswami and Gallant 2025). For example, the 2012 drought in the US heartland eventually affected 65% of CONUS (contiguous United States), of which 20% of the area experienced extreme or exceptional drought conditions, causing a global food security crisis along with \$30 billion agricultural losses (Boyer *et al* 2013). Even more concerning was the rapid intensification, going

from abnormally dry to the most extreme drought category (D4) in just two months, as monitored by the U.S. Drought Monitor (USDM; Svoboda *et al* 2002). This was not an isolated incident; several previous studies documented such flash droughts, like the 2010 flash drought in Russia (Christian *et al* 2020), the Southern China flash drought in 2013 (Yuan *et al* 2015), and the Southern African flash drought in 2015 (Yuan *et al* 2018). Moreover, studies show that there has been an increase in such incidents in various parts of the world, like in Brazil, between 1980 and 2015 (Christian *et al* 2021). Flash droughts threaten agriculture and food security by significantly lowering gross primary productivity (e.g. Ford and Labosier 2017, Christian *et al* 2021, Jing *et al* 2025).

The atmospheric conditions antecedent to these flash drought events are precipitation deficits and high temperatures, causing an increase in the evaporative demand (Ford and Labosier 2017, Pendergrass *et al* 2020, Shah *et al* 2023, Zeng *et al* 2023). Several recent studies indicated an increase in flash drought events under different emission scenarios (e.g. Christian *et al* 2021, 2023, Naumann *et al* 2021, Sreeparvathy and Srinivas 2022, among others). Yuan *et al* (2023) in their study highlighted that the global shift from slow-onset droughts to flash droughts is driven by climate change caused by human activities. A study by Yuan *et al* (2019) showed that greenhouse gas emissions (GHGs) are responsible for more than 77% of the observed increase in flash drought incidents across China. Thus, it can be said that anthropogenic warming plays a role in altering these flash drought events into the future. Europe encompasses alpine, maritime, Mediterranean, and continental climates; such climatic and environmental heterogeneity demands more focused regional study to see the development of flash drought in future. A study by Christian *et al* (2024) analysed existing research on flash droughts, dividing them by region, countries and global scale, highlighting the lack of regional studies for Europe (four in total by then) compared to other regions like the US and China (48 each). Thus, it can be said that despite these recent advancements, there is a lack of assessment of how flash droughts may evolve in terms of different global warming scenarios in the European context.

The aim of this study is to address the lack of regional studies specific to Europe, focusing on how flash droughts may change with different levels of global warming for better policy implementation approaches. A warming level-based ensemble of various projected models represents the development of flash droughts under similar environmental conditions, specifically temperature. This helps to reduce the uncertainties related to differences in climate sensitivity between models, which enables a clearer detection of regional patterns (Vautard *et al* 2014). We

analyse the frequency and spatial extent, along with regional variability, of flash droughts across Europe using the ISIMIP3b dataset, using pentad-based soil moisture obtained through the spatially distributed mesoscale hydrologic model (mHM). We examine rapid soil moisture declines to identify flash droughts. Additionally, the study investigates the underlying driving temperature and precipitation anomalies. At the end, the sensitivity of the frequency and the area are analysed with respect to each degree of warming. It will be helpful for policymakers targeting a particular level of warming-based strategies.

2. Data and methods

2.1. Meteorological input data representing global warming levels

Meteorological data used to identify flash drought events are primarily based on the Inter-Sectoral Impact Model Intercomparison Project (ISIMIP3b; Warszawski *et al* 2014, Lange and Büchner 2021), which is based on simulations from the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 6 (CMIP6; O'Neill *et al* 2016). These data cover both historical conditions (1950–2014) and future projections (2015–2100) under three shared socioeconomic pathways (SSPs): SSP1-2.6, SSP3-7.0, and SSP5-8.5, representing different levels of GHGs and socioeconomic development (O'Neill *et al* 2014). We use output from five general circulation models (GCMs): GFDL-ESM4, IPSL-CM6A-LR, MPI-ESM1-2-HR, MRI-ESM2-0, UKESM1-0-LL under each SSP scenario. These GCMs are used because of their structural uniqueness and collective representation of the broader CMIP6 ensemble (Rosa and Sangiorgio 2025). These data are available at daily temporal resolution and at the $0.5^\circ \times 0.5^\circ$ spatial resolution. Since this study focuses on different levels of global warming, we do not directly use the SSP time series. A period of ± 15 years around the year when that particular warming is reached in the different SSP-GCM combinations is used for the analysis (ISIMIP 2021, Lange and Büchner 2021) (see table 1 for warming level years). This period is decided on the basis of ISIMIP3b, which utilises a 31-year moving average (Lange and Büchner 2021), which also leads to the removal of short-term fluctuations in the data (Pierce *et al* 2015).

2.2. Methodology

2.2.1. Soil moisture simulations and conversion to soil moisture index (SMI)

Daily precipitation and 2 m air temperature (average, minimum and maximum) data from the ISIMIP3b, bi-linearly downscaled to $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$, are used to force the mHM (mHM; Samaniego *et al* 2010, Kumar *et al* 2013) to simulate root-zone soil moisture. We employ the European mHM setup, which has

Table 1. Years when different climate models reach specified global mean temperature (GMT) above the pre-industrial levels (in °C) under SSP1-2.6, SSP3-7.0, and SSP5-8.5 scenarios (obtained from ISIMIP).

SSP126					
GMT (°C)	GFDL-ESM4	IPSL-CM6A-LR	MPI-ESM1-2-HR	MRI-ESM2-0	UKESM1-0-LL
3.0	—	—	—	—	—
2.5	—	—	—	—	2059
2.0	—	2036	—	—	2036
1.5	—	2018	2047	2033	2023
1.0	2021	1999	2013	2015	2011
0.5	2000	1956	1988	1998	2000
SSP370					
GMT (°C)	GFDL-ESM4	IPSL-CM6A-LR	MPI-ESM1-2-HR	MRI-ESM2-0	UKESM1-0-LL
3.0	2084	2055	2082	2075	2050
2.5	2070	2043	2067	2060	2040
2.0	2057	2032	2052	2047	2031
1.5	2042	2018	2036	2032	2022
1.0	2022	1999	2013	2015	2011
0.5	2000	1956	1988	1998	2000
SSP585					
GMT (°C)	GFDL-ESM4	IPSL-CM6A-LR	MPI-ESM1-2-HR	MRI-ESM2-0	UKESM1-0-LL
3.0	2076	2050	2074	2065	2046
2.5	2065	2042	2063	2052	2039
2.0	2053	2031	2050	2039	2031
1.5	2039	2016	2034	2027	2022
1.0	2022	1999	2014	2014	2011
0.5	2000	1956	1988	1998	2000

been thoroughly evaluated in previous studies against multiple hydrological variables, including river discharge, evapotranspiration, soil moisture and terrestrial water storage anomaly (e.g. Rakovec *et al* 2016, Kumar *et al* 2020, Pohl *et al* 2023, Bevacqua *et al* 2024, Droppers *et al* 2024). Our analysis focuses on the top 30 cm soil layer, corresponding to the near-surface root zone, where over 50% of global root biomass is typically found (Schenk and Jackson 2002). This depth is important for vegetation, which is vulnerable to soil moisture depletion during flash droughts in the vegetation period (Moreno *et al* 2005, Fan *et al* 2016, Shah *et al* 2022), and can affect vegetation health (Ford and Labosier 2017, Otkin *et al* 2018, Mishra *et al* 2021, Sungmin and Park 2023).

To reduce the influence of short-term variability, daily soil moisture simulations are aggregated into 5 day pentads. Given the strong regional differences in climate, soil, and vegetation across Europe, we convert pentad soil moisture values into standardised SMI for each grid using the non-parametric Gringorten plotting position method (Gringorten 1963), see supplementary information section S1.1. First, we obtain the Gringorten-based distribution function curve over each grid for the respective pentad in the growing season for the historical period of 1950–2014. Then, we apply these historical distributions to the corresponding pentads in the future period (2015–2100) to calculate SMI values for each of the SSP-GCM separately.

2.2.2. Flash drought identification

We use the SMI to obtain flash drought events during the growing season (i.e. 19–55 pentads out of 73 in each year). For this, the respective pentads of each year are utilised for each grid to get the SMI based on soil moisture conditions in the future and then later flash drought events. Supplementary figure S1 shows the schematic of the flash drought definition. The flash drought is initiated when SMI falls from a mark above 0.4 to below 0.2 in less than three continuous pentads. Also, there should be a consistent decline in the SMI at the mean intensification rate of at least 0.1 per pentad, therefore fulfilling the condition of rapid decline (Otkin *et al* 2018). The flash drought event is marked as terminated when the SMI rises to above 0.2 and stays there for at least two continuous pentads, eliminating a single abnormal event of rise in SMI. Only the drought events lasting between 6 and 18 pentads were considered, ensuring the elimination of short-term abnormality and differentiation from long-term drought events (conventional droughts) (e.g. Yuan *et al* 2019, Mahto and Mishra 2020, Pendergrass *et al* 2020, Mishra *et al* 2021).

We obtain the flash drought events for the period 1950–2100 across Europe, which are further decomposed into three SREX regions defined by IPCC (figure 1(a)), viz., Northern (NEU) and Central Europe (CEU) and the Mediterranean (MED)) (Murray and Ebi 2012). These flash drought events

are then later used to synthesise the results at various warming levels according to the year in which that warming is achieved (see table 1).

2.2.3. Experimental design for analysis under various warming levels

Flash drought conditions, identified under each SSP-GCM combination, are analysed to determine their frequency and spatial extent across various warming levels. For each warming level, the frequency of flash drought is calculated per grid cell using an ensemble of up to 15 SSP-GCM combinations. This per-grid frequency is then normalised by dividing by the number of combinations available for that warming level, as some warming levels might not be achieved in certain SSP-GCM combinations

(see table 1). For each SSP-GCM in the event of a flash drought occurrence, the total area in that year is obtained during the 31 year period. These areas obtained through each SSP-GCM combination are then used to get a density distribution ridge plot for each warming level for Europe, as well as the three European regions (NEU, CEU and MED). We also conducted the analysis to examine projected changes in flash drought characteristics for various land cover types (cropland, pastureland and forest). The LUH2 (Land Use Harmonization², Hurtt *et al* 2020) dataset is utilised for this purpose, which provides annually updated dynamic land-use patterns at $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ resolution. It is to be noted that our analysis acts as an assessment of potential exposure of dynamic land-use classes to ‘climate-induced

flash droughts'. The full accounting of realised/actual exposure can depend upon various other factors such as physiological responses and CO₂ fertilisation effect, as well as land-management processes such as irrigation, which is beyond the scope of the current study.

Furthermore, temperature and precipitation anomalies are calculated from the ISIMIP3b dataset to understand how the flash droughts vary with changing temperature and precipitation anomalies under different warming levels, and where they are concentrated. For this, a 31 year ensemble mean baseline of 1 °C is calculated for the respective pentads for each grid, which are utilised to calculate anomalies of the corresponding pentads again for each grid separately. According to IPCC (2018), Masson-Delmotte *et al* (2018), in 2017, human-induced warming reached approximately 1.0 °C (likely between 0.8 °C and 1.2 °C) above pre-industrial levels. The 1 °C is selected as the baseline as that represents the most recent past global temperature. The 3 °C warming level is chosen as that represents the future projections if the emission path continues without sustainable policies and uninhibited emissions (Rosa and Sangiorgio 2025). The 1.5 °C and 2 °C are used as they form the central part of the Paris Agreement 2015. Finally, we carry out a sensitivity analysis to understand how the frequency and area of these flash droughts vary as global warming increases.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Frequency of flash drought in Europe under different warming levels

Figure 1 shows an overall increase in the number of flash drought events, with the results being more pronounced in the Northern and Central parts of Europe and less so in the Mediterranean region, showing regional disparities. Total count goes as high as above 30, implying an almost annual frequency under the highest warming scenario. The Northern and Central European regions typically exhibit higher baseline soil moisture due to more frequent precipitation. In such wet/transitional climates, flash droughts can quickly form when high evaporative demand coincides with short precipitation deficits; in contrast, however, the Mediterranean has a moisture-limited climate, so even if evaporative demand is high, actual evapotranspiration that occurs is less because the soil is already dry (Manning *et al* 2018).

Figures 1(e)–(g) presents the relative percentage changes in flash drought numbers. We can see the development of new hotspots and also the frequent nature of such events at higher warming as we move from 1.5 °C to 3 °C. Several areas, particularly in Northern Europe, exhibit a 100% increase in flash drought occurrence, suggesting a potential doubling of the number of events. The spatial map

of flash droughts indicates emerging hot spots of flash droughts in Central Europe, which historically were less impacted by such droughts. The sudden outbursts of brown spots at 2 °C depict it as a critical threshold. Along some coastlines as well, we see an increase in the events, indicating the possibility of some local maritime factors being responsible, like warm sea surface temperatures and persistent high-pressure systems, which can suppress convective precipitation, intensifying drought conditions in coastal Mediterranean regions (Wang and Yuan 2022). So, even though, lower synoptic variability in the Mediterranean, unlike in the northern and central European regions, limits the frequent atmospheric changes that can lead to conditions of flash drought (Manning *et al* 2018), the local factors coupled with coastal dynamics such as salinity intrusion and reduced freshwater inflows further amplify drought stress in deltaic and estuarine zones, highlighting the complex interplay between land-ocean-atmosphere systems in modulating Mediterranean flash drought vulnerability (Xu *et al* 2023).

Figure 1(h) shows an increase from around three flash drought events every decade at 1 °C warming level to more than 5 events at 3 °C. Box-plot also suggests that there is an increase in every region, but the effects are more pronounced in the Northern and Central parts. Mediterranean shows lower numbers in comparison; local hot spots, however, do exist along the Mediterranean coastline. There is a broader increase in high-frequency zones between 1.5 °C and 2 °C, indicating increased sensitivity and the widespread expansion of flash droughts. The Mediterranean also shows a slower escalation compared to the Northern and Central European regions. Supplementary figure S3 shows the coefficient of variation, indicating robust model agreement.

3.2. Spatial extent of flash droughts in Europe under different warming levels

Figure 2(a) shows a consistent rise in the spatial extent of flash droughts as global warming intensifies from 1 °C to 3 °C. Notably, the area at 1 °C warming is predominantly below 40% (around 13% area under the curve is above 40%), which is in striking contrast to more than 71% area under curve reaching above 40% at 3 °C warming. The increment implicates a gradual increase with almost linear amplification in flash drought extent. This increase is especially noticeable in Northern and Central Europe, where flash droughts affect more than 60% of the area in some cases, even at a 1.5 °C warming level, see figures 2(b) and (c). By 3 °C, the area reaching 40% in a given year becomes more common compared to lower levels of global warming.

Regional heterogeneity is evident across Europe with Northern and Central part demonstrating pronounced susceptibility with flash drought areas close to 47% at 3 °C compared to 36% in the

Figure 2. Flash drought area density distributions across Europe under different warming levels (see table 1 for centre years of the 31 year period). Panel (a) shows the density distribution of the area across Europe under different warming levels, with the dashed vertical line showing the area under the ridge plot that is above 40% flash drought area across Europe. The Y-axis within each row, i.e. warming level, is the kernel density estimate using Gaussian kernels with Silverman's bandwidth selection of the x-variable for that category, flash drought area here in our study. The flash drought area represented is annual. Panels (b)–(d) show the distribution across different regions of Europe, with (b) showcasing Northern Europe, (c) Central Europe, and (d) the Mediterranean. The number inside each density plot is the respective median value of the density plot. Panel (e) shows a box-plots of the area under flash drought across different European regions at different warming levels. Whiskers represent a difference of $1.5 \times \text{IQR}$ (Inter-quartile range) from Q25 and Q75, where Q25 is the 25th percentile in the IQR and Q75 is the 75th percentile, so the lower whisker is equal to $Q25 - 1.5 \times \text{IQR}$ (or zero) and the upper whisker is $Q75 + 1.5 \times \text{IQR}$.

Mediterranean at the same warming level, as shown in figures 2(b)–(e). Whiskers exceed 60% in both Northern and Central Europe. In contrast to these two regions, the Mediterranean is relatively stable, which could be due to a permanent shift in soil moisture conditions due to increased aridity (Silvestri *et al* 2025). This permanent decrease in soil moisture may mean that we do not see fluctuations as much from this decreased baseline soil moisture; these fluctuations cause flash droughts, so the Mediterranean might observe more long-term

conventional droughts instead of frequent short-term flash droughts.

We have studied area coverage in flash drought incidents across various land cover types as well (see figure 5, supplementary figures S6 and S7). We observe a similar pattern across various land covers. In croplands, the area under the curve exceeding 40% is around 67% with median lying at around 44% of the cropland area across the entire Europe. In case of croplands, Central Europe is expected to be slightly more affected than Northern Europe, both

Figure 3. Bi-variate heatmaps of flash drought events categorized into various 'bins' according to the prevailing meteorological conditions, i.e. temperature and precipitation anomalies going from 1 °C warming level (left) to 1.5 °C, 2 °C and 3 °C in the second column. The black outline shows the temperature precipitation anomaly region in which 90% of the flash drought grid/pixel count is concentrated. Each of the heatmaps is accompanied by the relative change along with the absolute differences (depicted by a circle enclosed into the bin) between a particular 'bin' corresponding to 1 °C warming level.

of which have comparatively higher areas affected by flash drought events compared to the Mediterranean.

3.3. Meteorological drivers of flash drought

Figure 3 shows evolution of flash drought occurrences under different temperature and precipitation anomalies at each warming level. Panel (a) shows the number of grids on which flash drought event occurs at 1 °C warming level at various temperature and precipitation anomalies. The 1 °C warming level serves as the baseline. At 1 °C, we can see the flash drought events are mostly concentrated in the moderate to higher precipitation deficit and small temperature anomalies (can be observed through the 90% contour line that encloses the bins in which 90% of the flash drought grids/pixels are located). As we move to the higher warming level compared to pre-industrial levels, we observed that the maximum occurrence of flash drought events (the concentration of clusters of higher flash drought count) shifts towards a hotter and drier climate, i.e. still moderate to higher precipitation deficits but higher temperature anomalies. This also hints at the role of precipitation, as even though there might be a shift of the number of grids towards higher temperature bins, the same amount of precipitation deficit is still required. That, however, does not mean that the role of elevated temperatures can be undermined. A study by Qing *et al* (2022) suggested that a high percentage of flash drought-affected areas is not always accompanied by

high temperatures. In our study, we can see a few instances at lower temperatures, where, in the case of extreme precipitation deficit, we can have flash drought, but the number is not significant. According to our results, for the most part, flash drought is accompanied by higher temperatures. Higher absolute differences and relative change can be seen from 2 °C onward. Even though there is a slight decrease in the flash drought events in a lower deficit and cooler climate, the difference is overshadowed by the significant increase in the hotter and drier conditions, as we can see from the absolute differences between the number of grids going through the flash drought (see supplementary figures S12, S13). Section S1.7 in the supplementary shows the regional results.

Panels (e)–(g) show the relative changes indicate asymmetric change, i.e. a more substantial and much more pronounced increase than decrease, leading to an overall much higher count of flash drought events at higher warming levels. The darker shade with higher absolute differences indicates the exacerbation of flash drought events caused by a warming climate. An overall increase in the number, as shown in the supplementary figure S13, suggests that flash droughts will be much more common in Europe with future warming. As the study by Řehoř *et al* (2024) also suggested that the course of flash drought episodes was also connected to increased temperatures and often connected to warm airflow.

3.4. Sensitivity of characteristics of flash droughts to warming

Figure 4 synthesises the aforementioned results in terms of the sensitivity of the number of events and the area affected to each degree of global warming. The results show that for both characteristics, there is an increase towards higher levels of warming. Panel (a) depicts the sensitivity to warming for the number of flash droughts. We observe that Northern Europe has the highest slope, so it is most sensitive to warming for flash drought events, followed by Central Europe and the Mediterranean. While Central Europe has the highest intercept, indicating a greater initial number of events, Northern Europe's higher sensitivity leads to catching up to the numbers of Central Europe because of higher sensitivity to warming. In all of Europe, we can observe that for the period of those 31 years, with each degree increase in global warming compared to pre-industrial levels, we observe around three more flash drought events. This is approximately one more event during each decade for each degree of warming.

Similarly, figure 4(b) presents the sensitivity of the area of flash drought to warming. Here, as well, Northern Europe exhibits the highest slope, showing higher sensitivity, followed by Central Europe and the Mediterranean. Since the area of Central Europe is more than that of Northern Europe, the overall area under flash drought is greater in the case of Central Europe. We can see from the slope of the entire Europe that for each degree increase in warming annually, more than 6% of the area will come under flash droughts. In both cases, the Mediterranean has the lowest slope and intercept, but still, there is an overall increase in the frequency and area in the Mediterranean as well. So far in our study, we have seen that flash drought affects more humid regions like Northern Europe and Central Europe compared

to the more arid regions like the Mediterranean. This is in agreement with Yuan *et al* (2023), which points out that flash droughts tend to occur more often than slow droughts over humid regions with lower aridity.

In case of specific land cover types (figure 5, supplementary figures S6, S7), croplands are expected to have two more events with more land being affected in the case of Central Europe. Area under flash drought is expected to increase by 6% with each degree of warming. The area follows the same pattern as the number of events, with most of the affected areas in Central Europe.

3.5. Implications and discussions

Flash drought frequency historically has increased not just across Europe (Shah *et al* 2022) but across the globe (Christian *et al* 2021). There is a shift happening towards the flash drought (Yuan *et al* 2019) because of the anthropogenic causes (GHG emissions). Even though there have been many studies highlighting the unprecedented increase in conventional droughts in recent years (Hari *et al* 2020, Büntgen *et al* 2021, Rakovec *et al* 2022), more studies are required in the field of flash droughts. Several recent studies like Sreeparvathy and Srinivas (2022) have indicated an increase in such events, especially in higher emission scenarios like SSP585. In general, soil moisture droughts are expected to rise due to anthropogenic causes (Samaniego *et al* 2018), so due to increased evaporative demand exacerbated by increased temperature and precipitation deficits, flash droughts are projected to be more frequent. Study by Gu *et al* (2025) suggested flash droughts accompanied by extreme heat exhibit higher severity and longer recovery time than flash droughts without extreme heat which also raises alarms regarding occurrence of such events at higher warming. Flash drought with other compound extremes like a concurrent heatwave

can impose an additional significant threat to our agricultural crops and ecosystems, as highlighted in a regional study by Wang *et al* (2023) how concurrent heatwaves can cause temporally shorter but faster-occurring flash droughts.

In our analysis, the assumption of linear escalation should be viewed as a first-order approximation that simplifies complex, potentially nonlinear responses. It is true that a more complex relation can be established, but that will lead to more uncertainty, as we have only four warming levels (i.e. four points to represent on the x -axis). Also, we have not extrapolated our results, and within these four points, we can see that the linear fit is giving satisfactory results. The purpose of this study was to establish such results for Europe that can be utilised for policy relevance. Our study reveals a positive sensitivity of flash droughts in Europe to each degree of rise in global warming. While previous projection studies exist, examining these projections in the context of rising warming levels is crucial for policymakers to develop warming-level-based strategies. Our findings

align with global projections, such as Yuan *et al* (2023), which anticipate more flash drought occurrences across the globe, especially over relatively more humid regions like Europe. This phenomenon can be attributed to the fact that, as evapotranspiration over these regions is energy-limited, enhanced radiation due to reduced cloud cover leads to an increase in evapotranspiration and speeds up drought onset. Importantly, Yuan *et al* (2023)'s global analysis also indicates a more rapid development and higher frequency of flash droughts towards Northern Europe, similar to the findings of our study.

Higher emission scenarios are of amplified threat (Sreeparvathy and Srinivas 2022) as these are the ones that will cause higher warming levels. Our study demonstrates that these higher warming levels carry an increased risk, especially beyond the pivotal 1.5 °C threshold. Some regional studies within Europe, e.g. Noguera *et al* (2020), show the higher occurrence in summer (the growing season in our study) and that 40% of all droughts were characterised by rapid development. We also found that Spain, among many

other regions, emerges as a new hotspot for such flash drought events. A study by Sungmin and Park (2023) shows the rapid vegetation stress caused by these events, amplifying the need for adaptation and mitigation measures. Our study shows the importance of Paris Agreement (2015) to keep the global warming 'well below 2 °C above pre-industrial levels and pursuing efforts to limit the temperature increase to 1.5 °C above pre-industrial levels' (Climate Action Tracker 2021).

4. Conclusions

We have quantified the sensitivity of flash drought frequency and affected area across Europe with each degree of global warming. Our analysis indicates that as the global temperature rises, Europe will experience a significant increase in the number of flash drought events. Furthermore, areas historically less susceptible to these events may not be safe, leading to the development of new flash drought hotspots. It is expected that there will be one additional flash drought event per decade for each degree of warming. The spatial extent of the area under flash drought is expected to increase by 6% with each degree rise in global warming in Europe. Our study also reveals that precipitation anomalies towards the deficit in conjunction with elevated temperatures are the drivers behind the increase in flash drought events in the future.

This study also provides a framework that can be adopted for other regional-level studies or global-scale assessments. Further study is needed to understand the impacts associated with such flash droughts and to identify effective mitigation and adaptation measures. Another aspect of future study could be to explore how large-scale atmospheric phenomena affect the occurrence of such events as Chen *et al* (2019) found out that flash droughts over the United States are largely related to La Niña episodes or as the study by Mahto and Mishra (2023) found out that positive phase of El Niño Southern Oscillation influences flash drought co-occurrence in 10 out of 16 major cropland regions and remains a dominating factor of flash droughts co-occurrence in the future. Another aspect could be to explore how vegetation and its type affect flash drought, which will require a regional study as well, as the study by Sungmin and Park (2024) shows heterogeneous responses to ecological impacts. These aspects are currently out of the scope of this study but can be further extended comprehensively in future studies. It can be concluded that with rise in warming flash drought are going to rise in numbers and in area. With its detrimental effect on crops and with agricultural losses identified as the 'Key risk 2' by IPCC (Bednar-Friedl *et al* 2022), flash droughts require our attention to mitigate such risks to agricultural crops and natural ecosystems.

Data availability statement

The soil moisture data obtained through mHM and the corresponding flash drought data can be found at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17300658>. The ISIMIP3b bias-adjusted atmospheric climate input data (v1.1) for the 5 GCMs can be obtained from the ISIMIP repository <https://doi.org/10.48364/ISIMIP.482153.1>. The study then uses warming levels provided by the ISIMIP protocol website www.isimip.org/protocol/isimip3b-temperature-thresholds-and-time-slices/ to determine the years corresponding to different warming levels under various scenarios and GCMs. ERA5 data can be obtained from the Copernicus Climate Change Service (C3S) Climate Data Store: <https://doi.org/10.24381/cds.adbb2d47>. The source of the mesoscale Hydrologic model used in the study can be found at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8279545>. The remaining code used in this study is available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Supplementary Information available at <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/ae11c8/data1>.

Acknowledgments

This research has been supported by the Grant Agency of the Czech Republic for Project No. 23-520 08056S. DY also acknowledges support from the AdAgriF project (CZ.02.01.01/00/22_008/0004635). Computational resources were provided by the e-INFRA CZ project (ID:90254), supported by the Ministry of Education, Youth and Sports of the Czech Republic. DY was also funded by the Internal Grant Agency (Project No: 2024B0024), OR also acknowledges the Research Excellence in Environmental Sciences (REES) project, both by the Faculty of Environmental Sciences, Czech University of Life Sciences Prague. We would like to thank two anonymous reviewers for their valuable comments during the review process.

Author contributions

Devvrat Yadav 0009-0002-1171-7261
Data curation (lead), Conceptualization (equal), Formal analysis (lead), Investigation (lead), Methodology (lead), Software (lead), Validation (lead), Visualization (lead), Writing – original draft (lead), Writing – review & editing (lead)

Rohini Kumar 0000-0002-4396-2037
Conceptualization (equal), Methodology (equal), Supervision (equal), Writing – review & editing (equal), Visualization (equal), Investigation (equal)

Jignesh Shah 0000-0003-0888-2960
Data curation (supporting), Methodology (equal),
Software (equal), Writing – review &
editing (supporting)

Vishal Thakur 0000-0003-2864-9517
Data curation (supporting),
Investigation (supporting), Writing – review &
editing (equal), Software (supporting)

Martin Hanel 0000-0001-8317-6711
Investigation (supporting), Project
administration (equal), Software (supporting)

Oldrich Rakovec 0000-0003-2451-3305
Conceptualization (equal), Funding
acquisition (equal), Investigation (equal),
Methodology (equal), Project
administration (equal), Supervision (equal),
Visualization (equal), Writing – review &
editing (equal)

References

- Bednar-Friedl B et al 2022 Europe: from chapters and cross-chapter papers *Climate Change 2022: Impacts, Adaptation and Vulnerability* (Cambridge University Press) pp 1817–927
- Bevacqua E, Rakovec O, Schumacher D L, Kumar R, Thober S, Samaniego L, Seneviratne S I and Zscheischler J 2024 Direct and lagged climate change effects intensified the 2022 European drought *Nat. Geosci.* **17** 1–8
- Boyer J et al 2013 The US drought of 2012 in perspective: a call to action *Glob. Food Secur.* **2** 139–43
- Büntgen U et al 2021 Recent European drought extremes beyond common era background variability *Nat. Geosci.* **14** 190–6
- Chen L G, Gottschalck J, Hartman A, Miskus D, Tinker R and Artusa A 2019 Flash drought characteristics based on US drought monitor *Atmosphere* **10** 498
- Christian J I, Basara J B, Hunt E D, Otkin J A, Furtado J C, Mishra V, Xiao X and Randall R M 2021 Global distribution, trends and drivers of flash drought occurrence *Nat. Commun.* **12** 6330
- Christian J I, Basara J B, Hunt E D, Otkin J A and Xiao X 2020 Flash drought development and cascading impacts associated with the 2010 Russian heatwave *Environ. Res. Lett.* **15** 094078
- Christian J I, Basara J B, Otkin J A and Hunt E D 2019 Regional characteristics of flash droughts across the United States *Environ. Res. Commun.* **1** 125004
- Christian J I, Hobbins M, Hoell A, Otkin J A, Ford T W, Cravens A E, Powlen K A, Wang H and Mishra V 2024 Flash drought: a state of the science review *Wiley Interdiscip. Rev.: Water* **11** e1714
- Christian J I, Martin E R, Basara J B, Furtado J C, Otkin J A, Lowman L E, Hunt E D, Mishra V and Xiao X 2023 Global projections of flash drought show increased risk in a warming climate *Commun. Earth Environ.* **4** 165
- Climate Action Tracker 2021 Climate action tracker (available at: <https://climateactiontracker.org/methodology/paris-temperature-goal/>) (Accessed 4 October 2025)
- Droppers B et al 2024 Multi-model hydrological reference dataset over continental Europe and an African basin *Sci. Data* **11** 1009
- Fan J, McConkey B, Wang H and Janzen H 2016 Root distribution by depth for temperate agricultural crops *Field Crops Res.* **189** 68–74
- Ford T W and Labosier C F 2017 Meteorological conditions associated with the onset of flash drought in the eastern United States *Agric. For. Meteorol.* **247** 414–23
- Goswami P and Gallant A J 2025 Understanding drought onset: What makes flash droughts different from conventional droughts? *Weather Clim. Extremes* **49** 100782
- Gringorten I I 1963 A plotting rule for extreme probability paper *J. Geophys. Res.* **68** 813–4
- Gu L, Schumacher D L, Fischer E M, Slater L J, Yin J, Sippel S, Chen J, Liu P and Knutti R 2025 Flash drought impacts on global ecosystems amplified by extreme heat *Nat. Geosci.* **18** 1–7
- Hari V, Rakovec O, Markonis Y, Hanel M and Kumar R 2020 Increased future occurrences of the exceptional 2018–2019 Central European drought under global warming *Sci. Rep.* **10** 1–10
- Hurttt G C et al 2020 Harmonization of global land-use change and management for the period 850–2100 (Iuh2) for CMIP6 *Geosci. Model Dev.* **13** 5425–64
- IPCC 2018 Global Warming of 1.5 °C. An IPCC Special Report on the impacts of global warming of 1.5 °C above pre-industrial levels and related global greenhouse gas emission pathways (available at: www.ipcc.ch/sr15/) (*Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change*)
- ISIMIP 2021 ISIMIP3B temperature thresholds and time slices (available at: www.isimip.org/protocol/isimip3b-temperature-thresholds-and-time-slices/) (Accessed 4 October 2025)
- Jing Y, Wang S, Chan P W and Yang Z-L 2025 Gross primary productivity is more sensitive to accelerated flash droughts *Commun. Earth Environ.* **6** 34
- Kumar R et al 2020 Strong hydroclimatic controls on vulnerability to subsurface nitrate contamination across Europe *Nat. Commun.* **11** 6302
- Kumar R, Samaniego L and Attinger S 2013 Implications of distributed hydrologic model parameterization on water fluxes at multiple scales and locations *Water Resour. Res.* **49** 360–79
- Lange S and Büchner M 2021 ISIMIP3B bias-adjusted atmospheric climate input data (v1. 1) (available at: https://publications.pik-potsdam.de/pubman/item/item_26187)
- Mahto S S and Mishra V 2020 Dominance of summer monsoon flash droughts in India *Environ. Res. Lett.* **15** 104061
- Mahto S S and Mishra V 2023 Increasing risk of simultaneous occurrence of flash drought in major global croplands *Environ. Res. Lett.* **18** 044044
- Manning C, Widmann M, Bevacqua E, Van Loon A F, Maraun D and Vrac M 2018 Soil moisture drought in Europe: a compound event of precipitation and potential evapotranspiration on multiple time scales *J. Hydrometeorol.* **19** 1255–71
- Masson-Delmotte V et al 2018 Global warming of 1.5 c: An ipcc special report on impacts of global warming of 1.5 c above pre-industrial levels and related global greenhouse gas emission pathways, in the context of strengthening the global response to the threat of climate change, sustainable development and efforts to eradicate poverty (<https://doi.org/10.1017/9781009157940.001>)
- Mishra V, Aadhar S and Mahto S S 2021 Anthropogenic warming and intraseasonal summer monsoon variability amplify the risk of future flash droughts in India *npj Clim. Atmos. Sci.* **4** 1–10
- Moreno G, Obrador J J, Cubera E and Dupraz C 2005 Fine root distribution in dehesas of central-western Spain *Plant Soil* **277** 153–62
- Murray V and Ebi K L 2012 IPCC special report on managing the risks of extreme events and disasters to advance climate change adaptation (srex) (<https://doi.org/10.1136/jech-2012-201045>)
- Naumann G, Cammalleri C, Mentaschi L and Feyen L 2021 Increased economic drought impacts in Europe with anthropogenic warming *Nat. Clim. Change* **11** 485–91

- Noguera I, Domínguez-Castro F and Vicente-Serrano S M 2020 Characteristics and trends of flash droughts in Spain, 1961–2018 *Ann. New York Acad. Sci.* **1472** 155–72
- O'Neill B C et al 2016 The scenario model intercomparison project (scenariomip) for CMIP6 *Geosci. Model Dev.* **9** 3461–82
- O'Neill B C, Kriegler E, Riahi K, Ebi K L, Hallegatte S, Carter T R, Mathur R and Van Vuuren D P 2014 A new scenario framework for climate change research: the concept of shared socioeconomic pathways *Clim. Change* **122** 387–400
- Otkin J A, Svoboda M, Hunt E D, Ford T W, Anderson M C, Hain C and Basara J B 2018 Flash droughts: a review and assessment of the challenges imposed by rapid-onset droughts in the United States *Bull. Am. Meteorol. Soc.* **99** 911–9
- Pendergrass A G et al 2020 Flash droughts present a new challenge for subseasonal-to-seasonal prediction *Nat. Clim. Change* **10** 191–9
- Pierce D W, Cayan D R, Maurer E P, Abatzoglou J T and Hegewisch K C 2015 Improved bias correction techniques for hydrological simulations of climate change *J. Hydrometeorol.* **16** 2421–42
- Pohl F, Rakovec O, Rebmann C, Hildebrandt A, Boeing F, Hermanns F, Attinger S, Samaniego L and Kumar R 2023 Long-term daily hydrometeorological drought indices, soil moisture and evapotranspiration for icos sites *Sci. Data* **10** 281
- Pulwarty R S and Sivakumar M V 2014 Information systems in a changing climate: Early warnings and drought risk management *Weather Clim. Extremes* **3** 14–21
- Qing Y, Wang S, Ancell B C and Yang Z-L 2022 Accelerating flash droughts induced by the joint influence of soil moisture depletion and atmospheric aridity *Nat. Commun.* **13** 1139
- Rakovec O, Kumar R, Mai J, Cuntz M, Thober S, Zink M, Attinger S, Schäfer D, Schrön M and Samaniego L 2016 Multiscale and multivariate evaluation of water fluxes and states over European river basins *J. Hydrometeorol.* **17** 287–307
- Rakovec O, Samaniego L, Hari V, Markonis Y, Moravec V, Thober S, Hanel M and Kumar R 2022 The 2018–2020 multi-year drought sets a new benchmark in Europe *Earth's Future* **10** e2021EF002394
- Řehoř J, Brázdil R, Trnka M and Balek J 2024 Flash droughts in central Europe and their circulation drivers *Clim. Dyn.* **62** 1107–21
- Rosa L and Sangiorgio M 2025 Global water gaps under future warming levels *Nat. Commun.* **16** 1192
- Samaniego L, Kumar R and Attinger S 2010 Multiscale parameter regionalization of a grid-based hydrologic model at the mesoscale *Water Resour. Res.* **46** W05523
- Samaniego L, Thober S, Kumar R, Wanders N, Rakovec O, Pan M, Zink M, Sheffield J, Wood E F and Marx A 2018 Anthropogenic warming exacerbates European soil moisture droughts *Nat. Clim. Change* **8** 421–6
- Schenk H J and Jackson R B 2002 The global biogeography of roots *Ecol. Monographs* **72** 311–28
- Shah J, Hari V, Rakovec O, Markonis Y, Samaniego L, Mishra V, Hanel M, Hinz C and Kumar R 2022 Increasing footprint of climate warming on flash droughts occurrence in Europe *Environ. Res. Lett.* **17** 064017
- Shah J, Kumar R, Samaniego L, Markonis Y, Hanel M, Attinger S, Hari V and Rakovec O 2023 On the role of antecedent meteorological conditions on flash drought initialization in Europe *Environ. Res. Lett.* **18** 064039
- Silvestri L, Saraceni M, Brunone B, Meniconi S, Passadore G and Bongioannini Cerlini P 2025 Assessment of seasonal soil moisture forecasts over the central Mediterranean *Hydrol. Earth Syst. Sci.* **29** 925–46
- Sreeparvathy V and Srinivas V V 2022 Meteorological flash droughts risk projections based on CMIP6 climate change scenarios *npj Clim. Atmos. Sci.* **5** 1–17
- Sungmin O and Park S K 2023 Flash drought drives rapid vegetation stress in arid regions in Europe *Environ. Res. Lett.* **18** 014028
- Sungmin O and Park S K 2024 Global ecosystem responses to flash droughts are modulated by background climate and vegetation conditions *Commun. Earth Environ.* **5** 88
- Svoboda M et al 2002 The drought monitor *Bull. Am. Meteorol. Soc.* **83** 1181–90
- United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) 2015 *Paris Agreement* (available at: <https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/resource/docs/2015/cop21/eng/l09r01.pdf>)
- Vautard R et al 2014 The European climate under a 2 c global warming *Environ. Res. Lett.* **9** 034006
- Wang M, Menzel L, Jiang S, Ren L, Xu C-Y and Cui H 2023 Evaluation of flash drought under the impact of heat wave events in southwestern Germany *Sci. Total Environ.* **904** 166815
- Wang Y and Yuan X 2022 The anthropogenic acceleration and intensification of flash drought over the southeastern coastal region of China will continue into the future *Atmos. Oceanic Sci. Lett.* **15** 100262
- Warszawski L, Frieler K, Huber V, Piontek F, Serdeczny O and Schewe J 2014 The inter-sectoral impact model intercomparison project (isi-mip): project framework *Proc. Natl Acad. Sci.* **111** 3228–32
- Xu H et al 2023 Development of composite drought indices for the coastal areas of southeastern China: a case study of jinjiang and jiulongjiang river basins *J. Hydrol.* **626** 130210
- Yuan X et al 2018 Anthropogenic intensification of southern African flash droughts as exemplified by the 2015/16 season *Bull. Am. Meteorol. Soc.* **99** S86–S90
- Yuan X, Ma Z, Pan M and Shi C 2015 Microwave remote sensing of short-term droughts during crop growing seasons *Geophys. Res. Lett.* **42** 4394–401
- Yuan X, Wang L, Wu P, Ji P, Sheffield J and Zhang M 2019 Anthropogenic shift towards higher risk of flash drought over China *Nat. Commun.* **10** 1–8
- Yuan X, Wang Y, Ji P, Wu P, Sheffield J and Otkin J A 2023 A global transition to flash droughts under climate change *Science* **380** 187–91
- Zeng Z, Wu W, Peñuelas J, Li Y, Jiao W, Li Z, Ren X, Wang K and Ge Q 2023 Increased risk of flash droughts with raised concurrent hot and dry extremes under global warming *npj Clim. Atmos. Sci.* **6** 134